

The Church of St. Anne, Anisaraki, Selino, Crete

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Entry tags: Greece, Religious Group, Byzantine, Crete, Religious Place, Orthodoxy

The church of St. Anne, located on the outskirts of the village of Anisaraki, is roughly 4km from the large village of Kandanos in the Selino province of southwestern Crete. Dated by inscription to 8 August 6965 (1457), the church is a single nave chapel with a barrel-vaulted interior and a saddle roof exterior. An original and painted stone iconostasis with a single archway opening divides the sanctuary from the nave. It includes, to the east, the images of two bishop saints facing the altar, and, to the west, the images of St. Anne holding the Virgin and Christ Pantocrator. The sanctuary apse shows the Virgin Platytera, hands outstretched around the image of the Christ child. Below the Virgin, four bishop saints, including St. Cyril of Alexandria and St. Polycarpus, are presented in roundels above the standing images of four co-officiating bishops. The triumphal arch, albeit damaged, includes the scene of the Hospitality of Abraham and the Annunciation. The deacon saints Stephen and Romanus the Melodist flank the altar. The north and south walls of the sanctuary include the images of St. Eleutherius and St. Anthony respectively. The nave is divided into two parts by a transverse arch. The barrel vault is decorated with scenes from the life of the Virgin and St. Anne. These include, for the life of the Virgin, the Virgin blessed by priests and the presentation of the Virgin in the temple, and for the life of St. Anne, the prayer of St. Anne, the meeting of Joachim and Anne, and Joachim in the wilderness. The niches of the northern wall include, to the east, the Archangel Michael flanked on either side of the niche by St. Anastasia and a male saint. The western niche of the north wall includes the mounted figure of St. George with the small figure of the boy from Mytilene who, according to one of St. George's posthumous miracles, St. George rescued from captivity. The healing saints Cosmas and Panteleimon, each holding the instruments of their trade, flank St. George on either side of the niche. Between these two niches is a large image of St. Anne feeding the Virgin. Similarly, the niches of the southern wall include, to the east, the standing figures of St. Demetrios and St. Procopius. They are framed on either side of the niche by St. Paraskevi and St. Thecla. The western niche shows three portraits of the donors of the church presenting a representation of the church to Christ. This includes the priest Ioannis, his wife, and the donor Vasilios. Christ can be seen in the upper portion of the niche reaching out his hands in blessing. The niche is flanked on either side by St. Marina and St. Kyriaki. Additional donor portraits can be seen on the westernmost part of both the north and south walls and flanking the entrance to the church on the west wall below the image of the Crucifixion. This includes the donors Michael, on the southern wall, Vasilios on the northern wall, George and his wife to the left of the entrance and Michael and his wife to the right of the entrance. Both couples on the western wall offer representations of the church to Christ. As indicated by the donor portraits, the partially preserved dedicatory inscription notes that the church was built and painted by George, son of Petros, and his wife, Michael, son of Petros, and his wife, and the priest Ioannis and his wife. Additional names can just be made out including Ioannis Kontoleon, Irini Tsagkarina, and Ath[anasios] Voula[k]as and his wife.

Date Range: 1457 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Anisaraki, Selino, Crete

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The church of St. Anne is located on the outskirts of the village of Anisaraki near the large village of Kandanos in the province of Selino in southwest

Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Single nave chapel.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. Anne

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. *Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete*. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See no. 69, p. 207-210 (with earlier bibliography)

– Source 2: Bissinger, Manfred. *Kreta. Byzantinische Wandmalerei*. *Münchener Arbeiten Zur Kunstgeschichte Und Archäologie* 4. Munich: Editio Maris, 1995. See no. 227

– Source 3: Borboudakis, Manolis, Klaus Gallas, and Klaus Wessel. *Byzantinisches Kreta*. Munich: Hirmer Verlag München, 1983. p. 221

Notes: Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. *Τοπογραφικός κατάλογος των τοιχογραφημένων εκκλησιών της Κρήτης*. Edited by K. Lassithiotakis. Heraklion: Εταιρίας Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών, 1961. See no. 147. Gerola, Giuseppe. *Monumenti Veneti nell'isola di Creta*. 4 vols. Venice: R. Instituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. See Vol. II, 333, no. 20; Vol. IV, 451-452, no. 26.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

–Other [specify]: The partially preserved dedicatory inscription notes that the church was built and painted by George, son of Petros, and his wife, Michael, son of Petros, and his wife, and the priest Ioannis and his wife. Additional names can just be made out including Ioannis Kontoleon, Irini Tsagkarina, and Ath[anasios] Voula[k]as and his wife.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

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Notes: Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. *Τοπογραφικός κατάλογος των τοιχογραφημένων εκκλησιών της Κρήτης*. Edited by K. Lassithiotakis. Heraklion: Εταιρία Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών,

1961. See no. 147. Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti nell'isola di Creta. 4 vols. Venice: R. Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. See Vol. II, 333, no. 20; Vol. IV, 451-452, no. 26.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

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Is the place situated in a rural setting:

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Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

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↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Single nave chapel.

↳ One single feature

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– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. Anne

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
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Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– No

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– Yes

- ↳ Groups:
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– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and

inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The painting cycle reflects the standard iconography of the Orthodox Christian faith.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans
– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives
– Yes

↳ Human narratives
– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: plaster, brick, stone

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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– Other [specify]: The painting cycle reflects the standard iconography of the Orthodox Christian faith.

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↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

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[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

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Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

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– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

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↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

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↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

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↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– I don't know

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– I don't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

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Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Church of St. Anne, Anisarakí, Selino, Crete, Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. p.207-210, no. 68

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